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COMPARISON OF PROPOFOL VERSUS PROPOFOL WITH LOW DOSE SCOLINE TO EVALUATE LMA INSERTION.

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ABSTRACT:

BACKGROUND:

The laryngeal mask airway (LMA) is an innovative device made for upper airway management and its use is well established in anaesthesia practice. It enables the anaesthesiologist to keep both hands free and obviates the need for tracheal intubation. Moreover, it does not cross the glottic opening, so the hazards of laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation are avoided in patients especially going for short duration surgeries ⁽¹⁾. It can be inserted with or without aid of neuromuscular blockade but the level of anaesthesia should be sufficient to abolish gag reflex and jaw relaxation.

OBJECTIVES: A prospective, observational study of **propofol versus propofol with low dose scoline to evaluate LMA insertion** was undertaken with the aims of comparison of two groups for different variables like ease of insertion, number of attempts, hemodynamic changes at the time of insertion, use of rescue drug needed for LMA insertion and incidence of complications (at the time of LMA insertion and postoperatively)

METHODS: The study was done in 60 adults (15 to 50 years of age) patients with ASA grade 1 and 2 who were undergoing planned elective surgery under general anaesthesia with spontaneous breathing.

Out of 60 patients two groups were made, 30 patients in group P and 30 patients in group P+S. Among them, Group P received Inj. Propofol 2.5 mg/kg and 5 ml sodium chloride (0.9%) I.V. bolus after 30 seconds and Group P+S received Inj. Propofol 2.5 mg/kg + Inj. succinylcholine 0.1 mg/kg diluted in 5 ml sodium chloride (0.9%) I.V.

Hemodynamic parameters, insertion variables and other data were noted.

RESULTS: Hemodynamic parameters remained consistent in both the groups, with more stable pulse rate and MAP in group P+S. No patient had any complication like coughing, gagging or laryngospasm in any group at the time of LMA insertion

CONCLUSION: Low dose scoline with propofol for LMA insertion reduces upper airway responses, lowers the requirement of rescue drug and also lowers the chances of apnoea and hypotension due to incremental doses of propofol.

KEYWORDS: LMA, Propofol, Scoline

INTRODUCTION:

Management of airway is one of the primary responsibilities of the anaesthesiologist. The Laryngeal Mask Airway (LMA) is an innovative device made for upper airway management. It was originally designed by British Anaesthesiologist Dr Archi I. J. Brain ⁽¹⁾. It gives the between the face mask and tracheal tube. It is widely used to provide spontaneous as well as control ventilation in patients. Since it does not cross the glottic opening, the hazards of laryngoscopy especially sudden elevation of blood pressure and pulse rate are avoided. LMA provides adequate control to allow intermittent positive pressure ventilation. Moreover, it is well tolerated at the time of recovery and provides clear airway in postoperative period. LMA insertion requires sufficient depth of anaesthesia and depression of airway reflexes. Among

various **iv anaesthetic agents**, the drug of choice for LMA insertion is **Propofol** because it is very effective in suppressing cough and gag reflexes. However, when propofol is used alone in patients, it can lead to involuntary movements and sometimes failure to insert LMA. If higher dosage is used, it may lead to untoward sequelae like hypotension and apnoea. If dose of propofol is not adequate, it can cause coughing and laryngospasm. Muscle relaxant Scoline suppresses laryngeal reflexes by depolarization of motor neuron end plate. But in normal dosage, Scoline causes myalgia, raised ICP, IOP, hyperkalaemia etc. It may cause cardiac arrhythmias. Studies are there that low dose Scoline improves the correct positioning of the laryngeal mask, decreases the chances of complications like swallowing, gagging and head or limb movement with minimal/no side effects.

So, the present study was done to assess the efficacy of propofol alone versus propofol with low dose Scoline to evaluate LMA insertion.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

Our study **propofol versus propofol with low dose scoline to evaluate LMA insertion** was undertaken with the aims of comparison of both the groups for:

- ✦ Different variables of ease of insertion of LMA
- ✦ Hemodynamic changes & number of attempts for LMA insertion
- ✦ Use of rescue drug needed for LMA insertion
- ✦ Incidence of complications, at the time of LMA insertion and postoperatively in any of the group

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Out of 60 patients two groups were made, 30 patients in group P and 30 patients in group P+S. Group P received Inj. Propofol 2.5 mg/kg + 5 ml sodium chloride (0.9%) I.V. bolus after 30 seconds. Group P+S received Inj. Propofol 2.5 mg/kg + Inj. succinylcholine 0.1 mg/kg diluted in 5 ml sodium chloride (0.9%) I.V. bolus after 30 seconds.

Thorough pre-operative assessment was done. Detailed history was taken. The procedure was explained to all the patients than **informed and written consent was taken**. Routine investigations like Hb/CBC, blood sugar, chest x-ray, ECG, RFT, LFT, serum electrolytes and special investigations according to history of medical illness were advised. All the patients were checked for adequate mouth opening and neck extension. Airway assessment was done using Mallam Pati grading.

Patients with Mouth opening <2.5 cm, history of an anticipated difficult intubation, pregnant women, patients with known acute coronary disease, with known hypersensitivity to study drug and with increased risk of aspiration were excluded from our study.

All the patients were remained nil by mouth for minimum 6 hours before surgery and 4 hours after surgery.

In operation theatre, I.V. cannula was inserted and inj. DNS pint started. Monitoring to all the patients with electrocardiography, NIBP and pulse oximeter. Baseline preoperative vital were recorded.

Premedication: Inj. Ondansetron 4mg + Inj. Glycopyrrolate 0.004 mg/kg + Inj. Fentanyl 1.5 µg/kg IV + Inj. Midazolam 0.02 mg/kg I.V.

Patients of both the groups received Inj. Propofol 1%, 2.5 mg/kg IV. The induction of anaesthesia was noted by loose of eye lash reflex. Then patients of Group P received 5 ml 0.9% sodium chloride or Group P+S received a bolus of succinylcholine 0.1 mg/kg diluted in 5 ml sodium chloride (0.9%) I.V.

After 30 seconds, LMA was inserted by standard technique while assessing the condition during LMA insertion. Incremental dose of propofol 0.25 mg/kg was given, LMA was not inserted properly or before try for second attempt. Total number of LMA insertion attempt were noted, but ease of insertion was observed only during the first attempt.

Then cuff was inflated with 20 to 25ml of air till the absence of audible leak. A proper airway was decided by a square wave capnograph trace, normal chest expansion and absence of audible leak. The device was fixed by taping the tube of LMA.

During LMA insertion, these parameters were recorded: Rescue dose of propofol required, fasciculations, apnoea, arrhythmias, conditions during LMA insertion [mouth opening (full, partial or nil), coughing/gagging (nil, mild or vigorous), head or limb movements (nil, moderate or vigorous), laryngospasm (nil, partial or total)].

The ease of insertion (easy, difficult or impossible) of device was also recorded. Ease was defined as no resistance to insertion in the pharynx. Difficult insertion was considered as resistance to insertion or insertion with one or more manoeuvres like gentle pushing and pulling of the device, chin lift, jaw thrust, head extension and neck flexion.

Vitals were noted at baseline, after premedication, at the time of insertion of LMA (0 min) and at 1, 3 and 5 minutes after insertion of LMA.

Maintenance was done with O₂, N₂O and sevoflurane (spontaneous ventilation). Inj. Diclofenac Sodium 1.5 mg/kg was given as analgesic.

After completion of surgery, patients were self-extubated.

Post-operative complications like myalgia and sore throat were assessed. **Statistical analysis:** Student's "t" test used for data analysis within in group & unpaired "t" test was used for comparison of intergroup data. Chi Square test is used for the condition of LMA insertion & complication. "P" value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups in Age, sex, weight and ASA grades which were comparable in both the groups.

Graph 1. Pulse rate changes at different time intervals

In our study, in both the groups, there was significantly decrease in pulse rate after premedication in both groups. At the time of LMA insertion, it was significantly increased. Also, there was slight increase in pulse rate 1 min after LMA insertion, then decreasing trend was seen in both groups at 3 and 5 minutes.

There was statistically significant pulse rate in both groups (intergroup P value <0.05).

Graph 2. Changes in MAP at various time intervals

In our study, in both the groups, after giving pre-medication, mean arterial pressure (MAP) was decreased but not statistically significant. Mean arterial pressure (MAP) significantly decrease from baseline value at 0 and 1 min in both the groups (P value <0.05) and then slight increasing trend was there after 3 and 5 min.

P value of inter group MAP shows that except baseline reading, MAP decreases significantly in group P.

Table 1: LMA insertion variables

Variables	Grade	Description	Group P (n=30)		Group P + S (n=30)		P value
			No.	%	No.	%	
Patient's movement	3	Nil	19	63.3%	26	86.7%	0.0369
	2	Moderate	9	30%	4	13.3%	
	1	Vigorous	2	6.67%	0	0	
Mouth opening	3	Full	24	80%	28	93.3%	0.2187
	2	Partial	6	20%	2	6.67%	
	1	Nil	0	0	0	0	
Coughing & gagging	3	Nil	30	100%	30	100%	-
	2	Mild	0	0	0	0	

	1	Vigorous	0	0	0	0	
Laryngospasm	3	Nil	30	100%	30	100%	-
	2	Partial	0	0	0	0	
	1	Total	0	0	0	0	

There was decrease patient movements in group P+S, which was statistically significant (P value > 0.0369). Mouth opening was also better in group P+S, but not statistically significant (P value = 0.2187)

Coughing, gagging and laryngospasm were not seen in any patient.

Table 2: Overall ease of LMA insertion

	Grade	Group P	Group P+S	P value
Overall ease	Easy	21	28	0.0195
	Difficult	9	2	
	Impossible	0	0	

Overall ease of LMA insertion was better in group P+S, which was statistically significant (P value 0.0195).

Table 3: Rescue drug and Attempts requirement during LMA insertion

		Group P	Group P+S	P value
Patients required rescue propofol	Yes	6	2	0.1287
	No	24	28	
No. of attempts	1	24	28	0.1287
	2	6	2	

Among 60 patients, six patients in group P but only 2 patients in group P+S require rescue propofol 0.25 mg/kg. Successful LMA insertion was done in 24 patients group P and 28 patients at 1st attempt.

Table 4: Complications at the time of LMA insertion

Variables	Group P	Group P+S	P value
Fasciculations			
Present	00	03	0.0756
Absent	30	27	
Apnea			

Present	21	28	0.0195
Absent	09	02	
Arrythmias			
Present	00	00	-
Absent	30	30	

Fasciculations during LMA insertion were observed in 3 patients of group P+S. Incidence of apnoea was present in 21 patients of group P and 28 patients of group P+S, which was statistically significant (P value < 0.05). In our study, arrythmias were not seen in any patient of any group.

Table 5: Post-operative complications

Complications	Group P (n=30)		Group P+S (n=30)	
	Number	%	Number	%
Myalgia	00	00	03	10
Sore throat	02	6.67	01	3.33%

Myalgia was seen in only 3 patients of group P+S. Incidence of sore throat was seen in 2 patients of group P and 1 patient of group P+S.

DISCUSSION:

The laryngeal mask airway (LMA) is an innovative device made for upper airway management. Since it does not cross the glottic opening, the hazards of laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation are avoided in patients especially going for short duration surgeries⁽¹⁾. It can be inserted with or without aid of neuromuscular blockade but the level of anaesthesia should be sufficient to abolish gag reflex and jaw relaxation⁽²⁾.

Various studies, Scanlon et al, Brown et al^(3,4) reported the conditions for LMA insertion with different I.V. anaesthetic agents. They concluded that propofol suppresses the cough and gag reflexes and was more effective in providing satisfactory conditions for LMA insertion. So, the agent of choice for LMA insertion was propofol.

But, when propofol is used alone in a premedicated patients, it can lead to gross patient movements and sometime failure to insert LMA. Higher dose leads to untoward sequelae like hypotension^(5,6) and apnoea. Vandana Talwar et al.⁽⁷⁾ compared propofol and thiopentone for induction and Inj. midazolam (0.04mg/kg) and Inj. Fentanyl (1.5µg/kg) as pre-medication for LMA insertion. They recommended a combination of propofol, midazolam and fentanyl to facilitate LMA insertion from their study. So, in our study we have used midazolam 0.02 mg/kg and fentanyl 1.5 µg/kg as a pre-medication with propofol.

A Yoshino et al⁽⁸⁾ studied comparison of two different doses (0.25 mg/kg & 0.5 mg/kg) of scoline for LMA insertion. Incidence of myalgia was higher in patients, who received 0.5 mg/kg scoline. Number of studies suggested a small dose of scoline (0.1mg/kg) to relieve

laryngospasm without causing prolonged apnoea and to facilitate LMA insertion⁽⁹⁾. It reduces upper airway responses and improves the chance of correct positioning of LMA. Our study with the use of propofol and 0.1 mg/kg scoline supports their studies in a way that none of the patient had laryngospasm or prolonged apnoea in group P+S.

In our study, hemodynamic parameters remained consistent in both the groups at baseline, after premedication and at the time of insertion of LMA (0 min) and at 1, 3 and 5 minutes after insertion of LMA with more stable pulse rate and MAP in group P+S which supports the study of various authors (Shahin N Jamil et al, Salem et al, K. M. Ho)^(9, 11). Low MAP 1 min after insertion of LMA may be due to effect of propofol.

Coming to various LMA insertion variables, more patient movements were observed in group P as compared to group P+S, which is statistically significant (P value <0.05) and supports the study of various authors, Shilpin Solanki et al⁽¹⁰⁾. Full mouth opening was observed in 80% and partial in 20% patients in group P, which was improved by 93.3% and 6.67% patients in group P+S. It was comparable but statistically insignificant, which supports the study of Shahin N Jamil⁽⁹⁾. There was no incidence of coughing, gagging and laryngospasm in any of the group, may be because we have well premedicated the patients. Overall ease for LMA insertion was seen in 70% of patients in group P compared to 93.3% of patients in group P+S, which is statistically significant (P value <0.05).

In group P, six patients needed rescue drug and more than one attempt for LMA insertion while only two patients needed rescue drug and two attempts for LMA insertion in group P+S. Fasciculations were observed in 10% of patients even with low dose scoline in our study, which was differ from the study of Ho KM et al⁽¹¹⁾ (17%) with same dose of scoline. Incidence of apnoea was 93.3% in group P+S compared to 70% in group P, may be due to muscle relaxant effect of scoline. Apnoea of short duration occurs even with very low dose of scoline in our study. Arrhythmias were not seen in any group.

Post-operative mild myalgia was also noted in 10% patients of group P+S and it required only simple analgesics and not much distressing. 2 patients in group P and 1 patient in group P+S were complaint about sore throat, which was treated with only hot water gargles and steam inhalation.

CONCLUSION:

A clinical study was carried out to evaluate LMA insertion with propofol alone or propofol with low dose scoline in 60 patients.

In our study, hemodynamic parameters remained consistent in both the groups, with more stable pulse rate and MAP in group P+S.

Among LMA insertion variables, quality of overall insertion variables was better acceptable in group P+S patients. No patient had any complication like coughing, gagging or laryngospasm in any group at the time of LMA insertion.

Overall ease of insertion was also statistically significant and better in group P+S. Only 6.67% patients required rescue drug and second attempt for LMA insertion in group P+S. Mild fasciculations and myalgia were noted in 6.67% of patients in group P+S, but they are not disturbing. From the present study, we have concluded that low dose scoline reduces upper airway responses to the LMA insertion and decrease the requirement of extra (incremental) dose of drug, so decrease the chance of apnoea & hypotension which occurred with higher dose of propofol.

So, propofol with low dose scoline combination gives significantly better condition for LMA insertion as compared to propofol alone.

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